

Building community data assets for life sciences through ABLeS - the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share

V2.0
14 October 2022

Steven Manos, Ove Johan Ragnar Gustafsson, Ziad Al Bkhetan, Rhys Francis

Australian BioCommons, Melbourne, Australia

Contact: steven@biocommons.org.au

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7213776

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

1. Introduction

The production of reference datasets and downstream data products in life sciences is a key activity of Australian research consortia including the Genomics for Australian Plants (GAP¹), Australian Amphibian and Reptile Genomics (AusARG²) and Zero Childhood Cancer (ZERO³).

Appropriate and scalable bioinformatics methods and compute resources are key to the production of these data assets, and the method and compute requirements for data production can be characterised in the following ways:

1. Bioinformatics compute use is episodic in nature, and happens over multi-year timeframes as research collaborations plan, prioritise, define collective goals, gather samples, and refine experiments (both laboratory and bioinformatics based);
2. Compute use is primarily driven by data availability: Compute is required when samples become available and experimental analysis has happened (e.g. genomics sequencing). These timelines are unknown in advance and subject to delays;
3. Software is often imported, complex, multi-language and not optimised for HPC infrastructure and HPC policies (e.g. queue system policies); and
4. A diversity of expertise and effective coordination are needed.

These characteristics are not readily supported by existing access schemes such as the National Computational Merit Allocation Scheme (NCMAS⁴) and the Adapter Scheme⁵, which require upfront plans that are not possible in sample-driven bioinformatics, and/or are time-limited to a maximum of 12 months.

In order to more readily support data-driven bioinformatics, the ABLeS (Australian Biocommons LEadership Share) program was established in April 2021 by the Australian BioCommons in partnership with Bioplatforms Australia, the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI⁶, Canberra), and the Pawsey Supercomputing Centre (Pawsey⁷, Perth, Western Australia) to support these characteristics and accelerate the production of data assets.

“The intention of ABLeS is to grow and simultaneously accelerate community capacity to construct, maintain and gain insights from community-defined and developed data assets (e.g. reference genome assemblies). It produces a flow of unique, one-of-a-kind data assets, that enable the research of entire communities to be planned and to proceed, in ways that would otherwise not occur.”

It targets established communities that are focused on a common research theme, create data for reuse, and have the ability to plan and prioritise species for study. The support available includes access to infrastructure, specialist expertise and a community led and shared repository of bioinformatics tools and workflows.

The ABLeS program will continue to operate through the second phase of the Australian BioCommons program from 2023. Access to high-performance computing, cloud computing and data infrastructure is

¹ GAP website - <https://www.genomicsforaustralianplants.com>

² AusARG website - <https://ausargenomics.com>

³ ZERO website - <https://www.zerochildhoodcancer.org.au>

⁴ NCMAS website - <https://my.nci.org.au/mancini/ncmas/2023>

⁵ NCI Adapter Scheme - <https://nci.org.au/users/how-access-nci/adapter-scheme>

⁶ National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) website - <https://nci.org.au>

⁷ Pawsey Supercomputing Centre website - <https://pawsey.org.au>

provided through the two national computing facilities NCI and Pawsey. Commercial cloud computing services will also be provided as the need arises.

2. Resources, onboarding and support

2.1. Compute and storage resources

In early 2021, ABLeS was initiated using NCI resources, with 16 million service units (SU) of compute capacity and at least 500 TB of storage available per annum on the *Gadi* supercomputer. Negotiations are currently underway with Pawsey, and those resources are expected to be included from Q1 2023. The full cost of these resources is being met by the Australian BioCommons, NCI and Pawsey. Access to other resources, such as commercial cloud, are being considered as ABLeS proceeds.

To efficiently and fairly utilise the available resources, the following procedure is applied:

- 5TB of storage is allocated for each ABLeS project at initiation.
- Every quarter, 100,000 SUs are allocated automatically for each active ABLeS project.
- Additional SU and storage resources can be allocated upon request at any time as needs arise.
- To minimise project disruption due to low resources a simple monitoring service checks the available SUs for each project regularly and notifies the project lead when resources are low.

ABLeS works with each project to ensure that communities are able to reasonably estimate and plan for their SU and storage requirements.

2.2. The Australian BioCommons Tools and Workflows repository

Collective efforts have been made by ABLeS, the NCI specialist support team as well as members of different life science communities to establish and maintain a shared repository of bioinformatics tools, workflows and databases on the NCI *Gadi* supercomputer. This repository represents a staging area where community members add tools that are critical for them and usually shared and required by other researchers. The result is that - in addition to the NCI centrally-supported applications - a repository tailored to bioinformatics community requirements is now available for any user of *Gadi*.

ABLeS projects are encouraged to contribute to this repository and online materials have been published on the ABLeS website⁸ to facilitate this procedure for all users. In October 2022, there were 70 bioinformatics tools available through this repository, some of them with multiple versions. Additional contribution to this repository can be made directly by users (the preferred approach) as well as by requesting a software installation that can be handled by the ABLeS and NCI support teams.

This collection of community installed tools also provides a basis for NCI staff to migrate commonly-used tools to the NCI centrally-supported applications, providing long-term availability, maintenance and support across all NCI projects.

2.3. Bioinformatics support

To mitigate the challenges associated with utilising the provided compute infrastructure, a dedicated *ABLeS Bioinformatics Application Specialist* is available who provides expert support and acts as a coordinator for the support provided by the computational facilities.

⁸ ABLeS Shared repository of tools and software - <https://australianbiocommons.github.io/ables/if89/>

Cross-cutting challenges are prioritised over project-specific ones. The specialist’s support includes, but is not limited to:

- Onboarding communities to ABLeS;
- Managing allocations on various infrastructures;
- Installation and deployment of tools;
- Maintenance of the Australian BioCommons Tools and Workflows repository;
- Management of workflows and databases, and making these easily accessible by users;
- Workflow optimisations and development; and
- Providing advice and recommendations on administrative and technical issues.

3. ABLeS access criteria

Just as reference data is not created for the benefit of a specific “one-off” research activity, ABLeS is similarly not aimed at selecting and resourcing individual research projects, however meritorious. ABLeS instead supports the foundational research stage, where the reference data is a precursor for widespread application in future meritorious research.

The ABLeS program deliberately does not apply selection criteria or run a competitive access scheme for access to the resources outlined in Section 2. The key reason is that such processes are seen as a barrier to the use of large-scale compute in bioinformatics. A core ABLeS principle is to reduce barriers to access and accelerate data outcomes.

Nonetheless, ABLeS does adopt a set of principles to ensure that the use of resources are aligned with its ambitions. As communities are identified, or approach ABLeS, which can happen at any time through the year, alignment with four key principles is expected:

ABLeS principle	Characteristics of an ABLeS project
1/ Common research theme	It is a defined cross-institutional collaboration, project, community, consortium, or some other collaborative construct, that is focused on a common research theme.
2/ Data-centric outcomes	It is producing reference and derived data assets that will be published to enable use/reuse by others outside the community.
3/ Community-level decision making	There exists a collaborative decision making mechanism to prioritise the bioinformatics work using relevant computational resources. This can be a formalised steering committee, a working group, or some other forum which is representative of the collaboration.
4/ Community-level expertise	The community has expertise which will drive and execute its bioinformatics agenda. This expertise offers a strong collaboration link with the expertise and support available through ABLeS, NCI and Pawsey.

By way of example, individuals or groups that do not intend to eventually publish their data are not considered.

Examples of ABLeS communities include the Bioplatforms Australia [Framework Initiatives](#) - such as *Genomics for Australian Plants (GAP)*¹ and *Australian Reptile and Amphibian Genomics (AusARG)*² - and medical research missions such as the *ZERO Childhood Cancer* consortium³.

4. Acceptable use and expectations

The Australian BioCommons engages researchers in ABLeS supported communities with the following expectations:

	Goals	Actions
1	The use of ABLeS resources is planned and approached with a level of care appropriate to their status as limited and consumable resources.	A focussed use of ABLeS accelerates progress towards the community's data asset ambitions.
2	The ABLeS journey is collaborative and involves the BioCommons, the research community, and the computational facilities.	Communities engage the BioCommons in an open and collaborative manner, with regular meetups.
3	Communities work to understand their tools, methods and the optimal approaches to solving the bioinformatics problems at hand. ABLeS will facilitate both the experimental/testing and production phases of computational analyses.	Reports are produced on their toolsets, workflows, methods, resource usage and quality assessments for derived reference data sets, to support and assist other communities. Reports on the structure and outcomes of both aspects are shared broadly by the ABLeS initiative.
4	The community's steering committee (or other oversight function) directs the use of ABLeS for data assets they prioritise.	That ABLeS is a standing item for discussion, and that forum plays a strong role in managing the use of ABLeS.
5	Resources used must be agreed upon / in line with the community's steering committee.	Resource consumption is in line with the priorities of the community.
6	The project lead is responsible for all use of resources provided, which will need to adhere to relevant facility processes and policies.	The project lead will monitor and manage reasonable usage of their project computational infrastructure allocations.

A requirement of ABLeS is that all users abide by the relevant access policies of Pawsey and NCI.

- [NCI Terms and Conditions of Access](#),
- [NCI Data Collections Management](#), and
- [Pawsey Conditions of Access](#)